

Keeping an Eye on Botnets in 5G Networks: Detection and Mitigation by NFV and SDN Apps

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Abstract—Current cyber-threats are also expected to produce disruption to 5G networks, among which we can highlight botnets as one of the most powerful ones subverting communication links today. Devices recruited by botnets can serve to cyber-attackers as stepping stone to flood 5G networks with useless traffic, causing services or 5G infrastructure elements to cease to be operational. The paper at hand presents the current demonstration of the 5G-PPP SELFNET Self-Protection use case, which strives to detect and mitigate botnets combining Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) Applications in a 5G-related environment, where their lifecycle management in an automated way is also integrated.

I. INTRODUCTION

The incoming fifth-generation (5G) of mobile networks aims at provisioning a scalable and dynamic infrastructure to meet the new and growing demands on the mobile broadband access, substantially supporting more users than the current 4G and LTE networks with higher requirements in terms of data throughput, availability, and lower latency. In this context, cyber security is nominated as a mandatory requirement that has to be treated accordingly with new and innovative solutions to address new cyber-threats in the new 5G mobile networks, without neglecting those already existing in today's networks. This supposes an even greater challenge to the existing ones in current networks, because the protection of the 5G infrastructure, as well as all the connected devices, has to be extended to a new dimension to achieve the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) established by the 5G-PPP [1].

- x1000 times mobile data volume per geographical area.
- x10 to x100 times more connected devices.
- x10 times to x100 times higher typical user data rate.
- x10 times lower energy consumption.
- End-to-End latency of <1ms.
- Ubiquitous 5G access including in low density areas.

Among these indicators, the higher mobile data volume, the higher typical user data rate, the higher number of devices connected to 5G, and the lower End-to-End latency (<1ms) are key indicators for the new cyber security applications. They can be exploited by attackers to subvert the proper functioning of the 5G infrastructure and cause disruption in user's experience. Concretely, the massive number of connected devices can be exploited by ill-intended attackers to compromise them, and then use them as stepping stone to flood 5G networks with useless traffic. As recent examples of cyber-attacks, two crippling Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks were launched in 2016, by Mirai and Leet botnets, reaching up to 650 Gbps of network traffic and making inoperative services of Amazon and Netflix, among others, for several hours [2]. Between these cyber-attack platforms, Mirai made use of a large number of Internet of Thing (IoT) devices, whose source code was shared on a hacker forum and thus it is now available for anyone to make use of.

Bearing in mind the considerations given above, concepts like availability, continuity, resilience, as well as guaranteeing the delivery of services in 5G networks are key terms for cyber security, which make necessary to evolve the current security management systems towards new, more dynamic and adaptive solutions. In this context, the Self-Protection use case defined in SELFNET [3][4] strives to detect and mitigate compromised User Equipments' (UE) shaping a botnet as potential sources of DDoS attacks [5], for example. Botnets are one of the most powerful cyber-threats subverting communication links today, which have also been identified in [6] as a security problem for 5G communications to address accordingly.

We present below the Self-Protection use case of SELFNET, as well as its current demonstration on how its NFV and SDN Apps can be combined in a 5G environment for detect and also mitigate botnets and how their lifecycle can be fully automated following autonomic management principles.

Fig. 1. Self-protection NFV and SDN Applications for botnet detection and mitigation in 5G networks.

II. SELF-PROTECTION USE CASE: PROACTIVE DETECTION AND MITIGATION OF BOTNETS

In SELFNET Self-Protection use case, botnet detection is conducted at two levels of abstraction because of the expected large number of 5G subscribers, basically by deploying two kinds of NFV-enabled sensors running at two Self-Organizing Networks (SON) control loops separately; namely:

- 1) High-level (*light*) detection of suspicious communications by means of a flow-based monitoring VNF, called Flow Monitoring Agent (*FMA*), proactively monitoring and analyzing big volumes of network flows quickly [7].
- 2) Low-level (*heavy*) botnet confirmation by a Deep Packet Inspection (*DPI*) VNF, deeply analyzing a much smaller number of peers identified as suspects during the previous SON control loop [8].

The proposed associated reaction for botnet mitigation consists on deploying and enforcing a virtualized and personalized honeynet as a VNF actuator [9], implemented in SELFNET as an NFV App, so as to isolate the botnet malicious activities from the bots or zombies detected by our proposal; that is, User Equipments (UE) belonging to 5G subscribers compromised and recruited by the botnet. This actuator is called in SELFNET as *HNet* (honeynet).

In addition to the previous procedures, detection and mitigation, it is also required an SDN-enabled actuator to apply *mirroring* and *diversion* rules in the physical/virtual switches to i) send copies of the suspected network packets to the DPI sensors (analysis) and ii) forward the malicious network flows to the HNet actuators (isolation), respectively. This actuator is called in SELFNET as *FlowT* (switches' flow tables), which is in charge of steering specific traffic policies through the SDN Controller (e.g., OpenDaylight [10]).

A. NFV and SDN sensors and actuators

Figure 1 illustrates the two VNF sensors described earlier to manage the double loop of detection, the VNF actuator to mitigate potential botnet actions and the SDN-enabled actuator to apply specific flow rules in the virtual switches (e.g., Open vSwitch –OVS [11]) for mirroring and diversion operations.

It is worthy to note that the FMA sensor is already deployed and configured, one per RAN, while the DPI sensors and the

HNet actuators are dynamically deployed in real time and on demand when needed. The FMA VNF is charge of collecting network flows from raw network packets with which the SON Autonomic Layer can detect alleged C&C communications by identifying similar behavior patterns between peers. Instead, the DPI VNF (when is instantiated) will report specific alerts to the SON Autonomic Layer to confirm that the UEs inspected are actually bots acting as zombies. In both cases, this layer is in charge of performing the *analysis*, *diagnosis*, and *decision* making to detect and mitigate botnets. (SELFNET is currently working on these processes, and they will be soon integrated in the current demonstration herein presented.)

Once the SON Autonomic Layer decides to “activate a new DPI sensor closed to suspicious bots” for further analysis, as output of the first self-protection control loop, a certain implementable action plan is sent to the Orchestration sublayer to start-up a DPI process, together with its proper configuration. If the botnet is confirmed by the DPI VNF, as a result of the second self-protection control loop, the SON Autonomic Layer will be able to start-up the deception-based response function proposed in SELFNET, deploying a honeynet through a HNet VNF where the bots will be isolated. In the following, their lifecycle management in an automated way is detailed.

B. Lifecycle management of NFV and SDN Applications

The execution of the two self-protection control loops is enabled, as discussed in previous sections, by a set of SON orchestrated actions applied in a fully dynamic and automated way on the NFV and SDN Applications. These actions cover therefore the full lifecycle and operation management of those self-protection VNFs and SDN Apps described earlier.

The first aspect of lifecycle management for self-protection NFV and SDN sensors and actuators is their onboarding in the SELFNET platform. This operation is managed by the NFV/SDN Apps Onboarding component in Figure 1, which basically provides an application catalogue service enabling one-click automated registration of both NFV and SDN Applications with a common approach valid for all kinds of sensors and actuators. Applications are onboarded as software archives which encapsulate the application logic providing useful information for their operation (i.e., configuration, monitoring metrics exposed, etc.). The rest of pure lifecycle management actions are enabled by the combination of the VNF Manager (VNFM) and SDN Orchestrator (SDNO).

The VNFM provides unified primitives for VNF instantiation, configuration, modification (i.e., scale in/out or up/down), operation (i.e., start/stop), and termination, fully compliant with the ETSI MANO principles and valid for any type of VNF (i.e., sensors or actuators). The SDNO enables common lifecycle operations for SDN Applications registration, activation and instantiation, leveraging on Docker-based isolation and management of applications [12] that interacts with SDN controllers for control plane purposes. On top of these, the App Manager shown in Figure 1 provides the abstraction of the whole set of dynamic operation actions (mostly application logic configuration and re-configuration accordingly) towards

the other SON Autonomic components. In practice, it resolves and translates autonomic operation intents (which are abstract by definition) into specific application actions; this is enabled by the unified encapsulation paradigm provided by the VNFM (for VNF Apps) and SDNO (for SDN Apps) components, which allow each activated and instantiated application to exhibit dedicated operation endpoints.

III. SELF-PROTECTION USE CASE DEMONSTRATION

A demonstration video can be found in [13] (“SELFNET Self-Protection UC S2 Demo”), which partially illustrates the NFV and SDN sensors and actuators described above running in a fully virtualized environment, dynamically deploying and instantiating the VNF and SDN instances in real time and on demand. The different steps shown in that video correspond to the second self-protection control loop: dynamic deployment and configuration of DPI or HNet VNFs for deep analysis and mitigation, respectively, as well as the actual application of the required network flow mirroring or diversion actions through the FlowT SDN App. It is supposed that a given number of peers have been previously identified by the first self-protection control loop as alleged bots and C&C servers.

The video steps are as follows, in order of appearance:

- 1) Deploy a DPI VNF based on Snort [14], as a well-known DPI tool to confirm the actual existence of a botnet.
- 2) Reconfigure through the FlowT SDN App the vSwitch’s flow tables to enable the network flow mirroring feature. This will send copies of the networks packets exchanged between suspected peers (potential bot and C&C server) to the DPI VNF for their deep inspection.
- 3) In this point, the vSnort will report alerts in IDMEF [15] standard format in case the inspected peers are maintaining malicious communications under a C&C channel.
- 4) Once the suspected UE is confirmed as a real bot, a HNet VNF is dynamically deployed based on a honeynet tool, in order to emulate the UE behavior with the C&C server and block potential cyber-attacks due to possible, future actions requested by the real attacker.
- 5) Reconfigure through the FlowT SDN App the vSwitch’s flow tables to enable the network flow diversion feature. This will hijack the network flows between the UE (real bot) and the C&C server, dropping them and generating new network flows for emulation.

In that prototype demo, conceived as a proof-of-concept, it is also demonstrated the current integration of the SELFNET VNFM (+legacy OpenBaton NFVO [16]) for fully automated VNFs lifecycle management.

IV. CONCLUSION

It is expected that 5G mobile networks suffer disruption on the proper functioning of its infrastructure components as well as on user’s experience, due to cyber-threats launching crippling attacks produced by botnets. This paper presented the Self-Protection use case of the 5G-PPP SELFNET project, which is devoted to detect and mitigate botnets through the combination of NFV and SDN Apps that will be dynamically

deployed on top of virtualized and distributed 5G infrastructures. A demonstration of the current progress on the use case have been described, and how to manage the lifecycle of the NFV and SDN Apps in an automated way by following autonomic management principles.

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